

The World needs the USD

Richard Beainy
Cesar Kamel
Satya Subrahmanyam
Marianne Younes

Affiliation:

CIRAME Research Center, Business School
Holy Spirit University of Kaslik
P.O. Box 446, Jounieh, Lebanon

Abstract

This study investigates the future sustainability of the current financial system with the United States dollar (USD) as the world's most dominant reserve and used currency, and evaluates possible alternatives such as a gold-pegged system as well as a possible futuristic crypto-based system.

Using data from the World Bank, IMF, ECB, Bloomberg, NASDAQ, and Yahoo Finance, the study uses three quantitative methods, with the objective of quantifying risks of using Gold and Crypto through GARCH model, projecting through a Monte Carlo simulation a timeline in which the U.S debt to GDP Ratio might surpass 200%, a threshold widely regarded as unsustainable, and finally using a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to evaluate which financial system is best for long term financial stability.

The results were unexpected, as the current US System proved to be by far the best among alternatives, with Gold being ranked second and Crypto based currencies being last.

Keywords:

Financial System; Cryptocurrency; Gold; Us Dollar; Reserves

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

At a time where for the first time this century, Central banks holdings in Gold have surpassed those in US Dollar treasury bills, changes are on the horizon, however as the study will discuss in detail, not all changes are good, and even standing still is better sometimes than moving, especially if the move is backward.

In 1942, when world war two victory became inevitable, the Allies gathered in Bretton Woods, New Hampshire, United States, and decided that never again will the world fall into chaos and war (Bordo, 1993).

Along with forming the United Nations (UN), with a goal of promoting long lasting peace, the World Bank to fight poverty and the International Monetary fund (IMF) to promote prosperity, they also agreed to use a single currency to keep the entire financial system in order, the currency chosen was the US Dollar, and this plan succeeded until today.

During Bretton woods agreement, and to make sure that this new currency would last for the longest time possible, and thus restore order and financial stability for centuries to come, a precious metal that is known to stand against time was pegged against the US Dollar, this not only protects investors in USD, enhance the success of the new system and renders the US community immune to hyperinflation, but also promote global trade and globalization.

Soon enough, 30 years later, President Richard Nixon made the famous announcement, ending the Peg of USD to Gold (Zoeller & Bandelj, 2019).

Since then, Fiat currency has become the norm not the exception, and the value of new currencies around the world became guaranteed by something much more fragile than Gold, Trust. And while the former would last for thousands of years, the latter is sensitive to changes even in a time span of days, to human sentiments and consumers' trust in the governments.

As technology developed and the era of printing books and newspapers ended, the era of printing money began. However, no matter how flawed the new system is, yet prosperity and wealth never peaked as much as now, and life expectancy increased at a record-breaking rate (Kamel & Beainy, 2023).

Finally, the promise which was made by the Bretton Woods participants while creating the new financial system still holds, and after 2 world wars within decades, more than 80 years have passed, and a third world war has been avoided repeatedly.

The new system works, and even though many countries tried, and some succeeded to abuse the new financial system, yet this system continues to promote wealth, peace and financial stability.

1.2 Problem and purpose statements

The main problem that the study attempts to analyze is that the current financial system, which has had a positive impact on humanity and on the Western civilization might be close to an end as several scholars (Eichengreen, 2011; Prasad, 2014) and reports (IMF, 2023; BIS, 2022) warn that its sustainability is under unprecedented pressure due to rising debt, geopolitical tensions, and alternative financial assets.

Furthermore, the alternatives are not clear and as scientists, an unclear future is nothing short of a disaster, especially that possible solutions, which include cryptocurrencies are far riskier as the risk report of this study will show.

Table 1: Timeline of the Modern Financial System

Timeline	System	Impact	Risk Level	Guarantor
1944	USD Pegged to Gold	Complete stability	NONE	Gold
1972	USD and Fiat Money	Wealth and Prosperity	High	Governments
Possible in the Future	Cryptocurrency	Chaos	Extreme	NONE

Source: 1944 Claim – International Monetary Fund IMF

1972 Claim - Federal Reserve History

Crypto Currency Claim – International Organization of Securities and Commission IOSCO

Therefore, the purpose of the study is threefold. First, to predict the significance of the threat of De-dollarization quantitatively, the second being to scientifically determine the time of the change in the financial system at a 90% confidence interval which is the threshold used in the study, and the third is to evaluate possible alternatives and their impact on the well-being of individuals.

2 Literature Review

To ensure a combination of recency and reliability, this review emphasizes primary and official sources (IMF, BIS, CPMI/FSB, SWIFT, ESMA/EU, SEC) and recent coverage from reputable outlets (Reuters/Atlantic Council) that summarize the latest data. The search draws its data also based on the latest IMF COFER reserve shares, BIS on dollar usage and market infrastructure, SWIFT RMB Tracker specialized in the Chinese currency (Yuan, CNY) for payments shares, G20 cross-border payments roadmap documents, CBDC/stablecoin policy frameworks (FSB/IOSCO, EU MiCA). Additionally, several new yet credible reports that investigate claims about de-dollarization were also examined. When combined, findings from these sources highlight that even though the current international reserve has become increasingly diversified with gradual yet steady expansion in alternative payment systems, however the U.S. dollar continues to dominate the global finance, and is according to those resources expected to continue dominating, at least in the short run.

2.1 The threat of de-dollarization

Recent literature continues to find very limited near-term decline of the dollar's centrality, despite active hedging and geopolitical drivers of diversification. The IMF's latest COFER release shows the USD share in allocated reserves rose to 57.8% in 2024 Q4 and slightly decreased to 57.7% in 2025 Q1, well ahead of the euro (20% approximately) ([IMF Data, 2025](#)). Moreover, the Bank of International Settlements (BIS) work through 2024–2025 emphasizes the USD's unrivaled role internationally: the dollar is on one side of the top nine FX pairs ([Bank for International Settlements, 2024](#)). The SWIFT's RMB Tracker shows that China's RMB accounted for 2.9 to 2.93% of global payments (6th place) by mid-2025—up slightly yes but still insignificant relative to the share of USD/EUR ([Swift, 2025](#)). It is worth noting that a combination of recent surveys (Atlantic Council; Reuters) judge widespread de-dollarization at the moment as slow and path-dependent, this claim is reinforced with significant network effects supporting USD dominance ([Atlantic Council, 2023](#)). The threat is credible in the long run (sanctions, geopolitics, and emergence of possible new payment rails) but is significantly limited in the near term due to the deep USD markets, the strengths of the legal and institutional frameworks in the United States, and the Fed backstop architecture ([Bank for International Settlements, 2024](#)). Kamel, Beainy, and Bteish (2025) argue that the weakness of this threat is in fact positive for international players in the financial system, both supporters and non-supporters alike, the study's SWOT analysis next will discuss just how beneficial was and still is, the current financial system.

2.2 SWOT of the current international financial system

The literature continues through analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of USD, Crypto and Gold as centric systems. Previous research show that the current USD centric system strengths can be summarized by a mixture of depth and liquidity of Treasuries and funding markets, benchmark role in foreign exchange FX (on one side of most trades), and robust crisis backstops (swap lines, institutions) ([Bank for International Settlements, 2024](#)).

The main weaknesses identified in the current system are the concentration risk and geopolitical externalities such as sanctions (Beainy, Khalil, & Kaspard, 2024), and persistent cross-border payment frictions in retail/remittances under correspondent banking ([Atlantic Council, 2023](#)). Furthermore, Public-sector infrastructure upgrades under the G20 Cross-Border Payments Roadmap (targets for speed/cost/transparency; ISO-20022, PvP), and wholesale CBDC corridors (e.g., BIS mBridge MVP in 2024) to cut settlement risk constitute the major signs of opportunities for the USD regime ([Bank for International Settlements, 2023](#)), also the stability of the current financial system (Beainy & Kamel, 2023) is acting as a catalyst for technological growth and research and development R&D. In the opposite context, using the dollar as a political tool, and growth of private token rails (stablecoins) outside central-bank money were considered a sources of threats ([Reuters, 2025](#)). The summary of this SWOT analysis suggests that even though the U.S dollar remain the essential backbone of the international monetary system, yet this dominance does increasingly rely on elements such as institutional trust, regulation strengths and technology, and it is therefore essential to increase this trust through a better monitoring of the institutions, keep the regulations up to date and modernize technology in the U.S dollar system continuously.

2.3 SWOT of a Crypto-centric system.

As for the Crypto-centric alternative, the multiple strengths existing in such a system could be resumed into four main advantages, such as programmability, 24/7 settlement capability (Xu, Chen, & Kou, 2019), the potential to bypass long correspondent chains and the ability to lower retail cross-border costs, especially if integrated with compliance ([Bank for International Settlements, 2024](#)).

The main weaknesses of this system are the run and peg risks and operational fragilities, and regulatory heterogeneity. Both the IMF and the BIS warn that most stablecoins are USD-pegged, introducing dependency and financial-stability channels ([Bank for International Settlements, 2024](#)).

Regulated stablecoins and tokenized deposits (supported by the implementation of the EU MiCA framework, with stablecoin provision effective June 30, 2024 and the broader regulatory regime became effective as of December 30, 2024), along with the institutional access via spot crypto ETPs which is following the SEC approvals in Jan 2024, and the movement toward generic listing standards in Sept 2025, are all considered as major opportunities for the Crypto-centric alternative (Lin & Nestarcova, 2019).

However, the literature shows some main weaknesses in this regime, mainly defined by tighter global standards (FSB high-level stablecoin/crypto tightening recommendations; IOSCO 2023 policy strengthening recommendations for crypto and DeFi) that could raise compliance costs and significantly decrease unsupervised growth ([Financial Stability Board, 2024](#)), finally, earlier studies by Chaanine, Mhanna, Verdie, and Beainy (2023) argue that a relatively new financial environment may negatively impact entrepreneurial performance.

2.4 SWOT of the Gold system

Viewed through a SWOT lens, the “gold system”, when analyzed independently of other systems, functions as a resilient anchor and a haven in international finance. Its core strength is in the fact that bullion is a non-liability reserve asset, valued precisely because it represents no one’s promise to pay, and it is precisely this neutrality that has underpinned a three-year run of exceptionally strong official purchases (each year above 1,000 tons), and it helped lift gold’s market-value share of global reserves to 20% by the end of 2024, even surpassing the 16% euro share in 2025 assessments ([World Gold Council, 2025](#)). Liquidity remains deep: London’s OTC hub clears over 20 million ounces daily and sets widely used benchmark prices, while COMEX futures provide price discovery around the clock and hedging capacity ([LBMA, 2025](#)).

These strengths however, come with notable weaknesses. Gold’s price can fluctuate sharply, as 2025’s record highs illustrate, which can cause reserve valuations to significantly differ with every cycles; bullion also pays no yield in forms of dividends, in fact it imposes custody, insurance, and logistics costs (Reuters, 2025). Market structure has also historically been more opaque especially when compared to securities markets, even though it is worth noting that transparency is improving via the LBMA Gold Bar Integrity (GBI) database to trace provenance across the supply chain ([LBMA, 2025](#)). ESG scrutiny is another constraint; the World Gold Council estimates the gold industry’s footprint at approximately 0.4% of global annual emissions, a small but non-trivial share for public reserve managers to weigh ([World Gold Council, 2025](#)). The opportunity set is expanding nonetheless. Surveys show more reserve managers plan to increase gold allocations; and the ongoing digitization and tokenization of gold, from bar-level traceability to the integration real-world assets into next-generation settlement platforms, could reduce frictions and make gold more mobile as a collateral without reintroducing the old rigid gold standard ([World Gold Council, 2025](#)).

The main threats to a potential gold system are related to policies and the market infrastructure. Sanctions have already fragmented parts of the market (e.g., LBMA’s suspension of Russian refiners and G7 restrictions on newly mined Russian gold). Also, episodes of tightness in London’s vault system during trans-Atlantic flows underscore how reliance on just a limited number of clearing houses and vaulting hubs can significantly increase operational and liquidity risk ([LBMA, 2025](#)).

Across the recent literature, de-dollarization appears to be a long-term risk rather than a near-term regime change. Network effects, deep USD markets, and the Federal reserve’s backstops mechanism keep the dollar central. A SWOT comparison suggests the USD system offers unmatched liquidity and best-in-class infrastructure but it also suffers from cross-border frictions and geopolitical externalities; crypto rails bring programmability and 24/7 settlement but face run, compliance, and scalability risks; the gold system provides a non-liability hedge with growing official demand, offset by volatility, no yield, and operational/ESG costs.

The most beneficial path forward according to previous literature is a hybrid approach towards the three systems; allowing political opponents to use the US Dollar, regulate private tokens

particularly in Bitcoin, and digitize collateral (including gold) to reduce frictions without sacrificing stability.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

Data related to international reserves were collected from the World Bank, however since Gold reserves are not directly available on the world Bank website, Reserves including Gold and reserves excluding gold were extracted, and the difference would be Gold reserves per country. Data related to Gold Holding versus US treasury holdings were collected from Bloomberg, for a 55-year period spanning from 1970 to 2025.

Bitcoin historical data were drawn from the National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations - NASDAQ, from 2019 till 2025 inclusive, in addition to Yahoo Finance supporting Nasdaq's Bitcoin Data and Gold Futures Data.

Data related to US Debt as a percentage of GDP were drawn from the International Monetary Fund IMF, from 2001 till 2030, noting that Data from 2026 until 2030 are Estimations.

Finally, Data regarding international reserves in Euro versus international reserves in Gold were drawn from the European Central Bank ECB.

Table 2: Data Sources

Data	Source
International Reserves	The World Bank
Gold Holding – Us Treasury Bills Holding	Bloomberg
Bitcoin Value	National Association of securities dealers automated Quotations NASDAQ
Gold Futures Value	Yahoo Finance
US Debt	The International Monetary Fund IMF
International Reserves in Euro	The European Central Bank ECB

Source: Compiled by the Authors

3.2 Data Methodology

The GARCH Model is used to quantify risk related to Bitcoin and Gold, mainly to be able to transfer the presumption of high volatility according to investor confidence into numerical data, with Bitcoin having higher priority as it is neither backed by central banks nor governments. Furthermore, in order to predict a timeline for potential unwanted DE dollarization, simple statistical methods would be useless according to the Chartered Financial Analysis CFA institute. Since the potential system change is new and might, hopefully, never happen, a more complex Monte Carlo simulation was applied.

Lastly, to Evaluate alternatives in comparison of the current regime, a Multi Criteria Decision Analysis MCDA is used to rank the current US System, with other systems based on either Gold or Bitcoin. The Current System will be compared to alternatives systems in terms of impact of Macro stability, settlement efficiency, liquidity and depth, legal and institutional quality as well as current rules and regulation, adoption and network effects, operational risk and Energy footprint.

Finally, the Current USD System along with the Gold and Crypto alternatives will be ranked from best to worst in different environments such as high inflation high debt scenario, early and late flips in the financial system, soft landing as well as the current, base financial situation. The approach the research used ensures through three different statistical analysis method that the study has both efficiency in terms of quantitative testing, and importance in terms of impact assessment.

Table 3: Research Methodology

Analysis	Statistical Method
Quantifying Risk	GARCH Model
Prediction of De-dollarization time	Monte Carlo Simulation
Evaluation of Alternatives	Multi-criteria Decision Analysis MCDA

Source: Compiled by the Authors

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction to Results (Previous Studies)

Figure 1: Dollar's share of global reserves declines to a 25 years low

Source: Bloomberg

The above figure sourced from a previous study, shows clearly a decline in the dollar's share, the largest decline in the 21st century, in addition, the below figure shows Gold surpassing US treasury holdings for the first time since 1996.

Figure 2: Gold surpasses US treasury holding for the first time since 20 years

Source: Bloomberg

4.2 GARCH Model

Table 4: Quantifying Bitcoin Risk (GARCH Model)

Section	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P> t	Lower Conf int	Upper Conf int
Mean Model	mu	0.1287	0.03062	4.204	2.62E-05	0.06872	0.189
Volatility Model	omega	0.1771	0.08552	2.071	0.03838	0.009472	0.345
Volatility Model	alpha[1]	0.1062	0.0139	7.639	2.19E-14	0.07893	0.133
Volatility Model	beta[1]	0.8938	0.0188	47.545	0	0.857	0.931
Distribution	nu	3.1845	0.125	25.479	3.4E-143	2.939	3.429

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python.

Table 5: Quantifying Gold Futures Risk (GARCH Model)

Section	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P> t	Lower Conf int	Upper Conf int
Mean Model	mu	0.0579	0.01186	4.884	0.000001	0.03469	0.08119
Volatility Model	omega	0.0082585	0.002519	3.278	0.001045	0.003321	0.0132
Volatility Model	alpha[1]	0.0374	0.004839	7.735	0.000000	0.02795	0.04692
Volatility Model	beta[1]	0.9575	0.00538	177.975	0.000000	0.947	0.968
Distribution	nu	4.6902	0.311	15.072	0.000000	4.08	5.3

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python.

Table 6: Bitcoin Versus Gold: comparison summary

Asset	Alpha	Beta	Alpha plus beta	Omega	Unconditional variance
BTC	0.10617	0.89383	1	0.177095637	
GOLD	0.037433	0.957474	0.99490629	0.008258454	1.621304425

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python.

Using 4,018 Observations, with Python as a programming language, Bloomberg, World Bank, IMF, ECB and Yahoo finance for data acquisition, windows PowerShell and visual studio code as an operating environment, the study transformed risk related to Bitcoin into numbers.

This quantification at a 95% confidence level, allowed to mathematically confirm the significance of Bitcoin Risk as the GARCH results confirm significant volatility clustering in Bitcoin and lower volatility clustering in Gold returns.

As per the tables Bitcoin has a persistence parameter $\alpha+\beta$ equal to 1.000, suggesting volatility shocks are long lasting, and in many cases permanent and highlighting the significant risk of Bitcoin. In other words, Bitcoin is clearly not stable enough to promote a stable financial system.

However, in the case of Gold we can see a slightly lower persistence at 0.9949, with volatility shocks that eventually mean-revert. The unconditional variance of Bitcoin is undefined due to its unit-root Behavior, while Gold's finite variance of 1.6213 supports its role as a more stable store of value.

The findings in these tables confirm and quantify prior research indicating that cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin included tend to exhibit extreme volatility persistence, whereas traditional safe-haven assets such as Gold, even though are volatile, yet eventually stabilize and can be used to promote a stable financial system.

4.3 Monte Carlo simulation

In this step, the study needs to calculate GDP and US Debt using international Monetary Fund Data, while IMF only provides prediction until 2030, the statistical mean and standard deviation were used to extend debt and GDP predictability.

However, even though total US Debt is increasing on a yearly basis, so is GDP, especially with technological developments such as Artificial Intelligence (Subrahmanyam Et. Al. 2024)

To take into account this increase in both variables a new variable Debt/GDP is used, with the goal of predicting the year in which the Ratio is above 200%, a ratio which is agreed upon as unsustainable according to previous studies.

Table 7: US Debt to GDP (%) according to IMF

Year	Debt/GDP
2001	53.3
2002	55.7
2003	58.8
2004	66.3
2005	65.6
2006	64.3
2007	64.7
2008	73.6
2009	86.8

2010	95.3
2011	99.7
2012	103.2
2013	104.5
2014	104.4
2015	104.9
2016	106.8
2017	105.7
2018	107
2019	108.2
2020	132
2021	124.7
2022	118.8
2023	119
2024	120.8
2025	122.5
2026	123.7
2027	124.9
2028	125.9
2029	127
2030	128.2

Source: ©IMF, 2025

https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/GGXWDG_NGDP@WEO/OEMDC/ADVEC/WEOWORLD/USA

Table 8: Probability of Debt/GDP passing 200% Ratio using 6299 Scenarios

Year	Nb of Scenarios	Probability	Cumulative Probability
2034	21	0.3%	0.3%
2035	53	0.8%	1.2%
2036	109	1.7%	2.9%
2037	151	2.4%	5.3%
2038	227	3.6%	8.9%
2039	213	3.4%	12.3%
2040	263	4.2%	16.5%
2041	280	4.4%	20.9%
2042	310	4.9%	25.8%
2043	326	5.2%	31.0%
2044	302	4.8%	35.8%
2045	323	5.1%	40.9%
2046	310	4.9%	45.8%
2047	314	5.0%	50.8%
2048	314	5.0%	55.8%
2049	312	5.0%	60.8%
2050	256	4.1%	64.8%

2051	276	4.4%	69.2%
2052	230	3.7%	72.9%
2053	247	3.9%	76.8%
2054	230	3.7%	80.4%
2055	227	3.6%	84.0%
2056	218	3.5%	87.5%
2057	198	3.1%	90.6%
2058	221	3.5%	94.2%
2059	179	2.8%	97.0%
2060	189	3.0%	100.0%
Total	6299		

Source: Monte Carlo Analysis using IMF Data

According to the above Monte Carlo simulation, there is 10% probability of reaching unsustainable Debt/GDP Ratio of 200% by 2039.

While the median year is 2047, at a 90% Confidence interval, the crossing year is 2057.

Notably, in all 6,299 simulations, the crossing year occurred before 2061.

Figure 3: Crossing Year Summary

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python. (Visualization through Excel)

Table 9: Monte Carlo simulation Summary

Variable	Score
----------	-------

Last Observed year By IMF	2030
Number of Simulations	6299
Horizon (years)	30
Median Year	2047
P10 Year	2039
P90 Year	2057

Source: *The World Needs the US Dollar* research Article using Python (Output).

4.4 Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

After the Monte carlo simulation provided a probabilistic estimate about the timing of a potential change in the financial system, a Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) was used to evaluate the impact of different financial systems.

The three system are the current financial system, USD Status Quo and the two most likely alternatives.

The first alternative is related to the past, the gold-anchored system, similar to the one that was agreed upon in Bretton-woods, and the second being futuristic and related to the recent Crypto currency technology, a Crypto-centric system which is according to most is the most probable.

The Procedure used seven evaluation criteria which were identified from literature as well as expert judgment, the first being macro stability such as inflation and volatility, the second being transaction performance such as settlement efficiency, the third criterion is liquidity and depth, the fourth is legal and institutional laws and standards promoting stability, the fifth is adoption and network effects, the sixth is a combination of operation and cyber risk.

Finally, in an environment where Energy and ESG footprint is becoming increasingly important, the final criterion takes into consideration which of the systems are best in terms of Environmental and Social Governance.

However, in terms of importance, ESG cannot have the same weight as Macro stability, especially since the subject of the study is a financial system, therefore each criterion was assigned a specific weight which reflect its importance, Macro stability and Liquidity receiving highest weight at 25% each, followed by legal qualities, standards and regulations for stability at a weight of 15%, Adoption and network effect received an equal weight as well, transaction performance weight is 10% and Finally, both operational risk and ESG were given a 5% weight.

Since according to both previous studies and historical data, the business cycle is rarely a straight line (linear) but is, mostly always a cycle that consists of an expansion, a peak, a recession and a through, five different scenarios were used to be able to understand how each financial system would work under different scenarios.

The Five scenarios studied are a base case, an early flip where accelerated de-dollarization takes place, a late flip in which there is delayed transition to a new system, a high inflation and a high debt scenario, and a Soft-landing scenario in which there is gradual adjustment.

Figure 4: MCDA Foundations

		Past Scenario: Gold System	Current Scenario: Dollars System	Futuristic Scenario: Crypto System		
	Base Case	Early Flip Case	Late Flip Case	High Inflation Case	Soft Landing Case	
Macro Stability (25%)	Transaction Performance (10%)	Liquidity and Depth (25%)	Legal Quality (15%)	Adoption and Network (15%)	Operational Cyber Risk (5%)	Energy and ESG (5%)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 10: Results Per Criterion

Financial System	Macrostability (inflation vol)	Transaction performance (settlement)	Liquidity & depth	Legal/institutional quality	Adoption & network effects	Operational /cyber risk (note: Here the lower the better)	Energy/ESG footprint (note: Here the lower the better)
USD Current System	0.7	0.8	1	0.95	1	0.7	0.6
Gold System	0.9	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.85	0.75
Crypto System	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python

Table 11: Results per scenario

Financial System	Base	Early Flip	Late Flip	High Inflation/Debt	Soft Landing
USD Current System	0.8325	0.8406	0.8420	0.8104	0.8479
Gold System	0.5900	0.5867	0.5862	0.6162	0.5798
Crypto System	0.4450	0.4445	0.4462	0.4403	0.4461

Source: The World Needs the US Dollar research Article using Python

Table 12: Ranking per Financial System (1 Best to 3 Worst)

Financial System	Base	Early Flip	Late Flip	High Inflation/Debt	Soft Landing
USD Current System	1	1	1	1	1
Gold System	2	2	2	2	2
Crypto System	3	3	3	3	3

Source: *The World Needs the US Dollar* research Article using Python

According to the results above, the USD based current financial system is best in terms of transactional performance, in terms of liquidity, legal and institutional quality as well as adoption and network effects.

It only ranks second to gold in terms of Macro stability or in times of inflation, also it ranks second to Crypto in terms of Operational risk and Energy footnotes.

While Environment matters, in terms of financial stability the current system is by far the most stable and secure, promoting wealth and individual wellbeing. Furthermore, in every part of the business cycle and under the current scenario and 4 other scenarios including early flip, late flip, high inflation and a soft-landing, the USD system excels by far over both alternatives.

According to results, US ranks one in terms of stabilizing financial situations worldwide and promoting a sustainable and secure financial and payment system worldwide. Gold ranks second even though adopting the gold standards again according to the study will pose significant transactional and settlement challenges worldwide.

Finally, the worst performing system is the Crypto based system, even though environmentally friendly when compared to the USD or gold mining and gold transportation, however it poses significant threat to global stability, not to mention the huge legal and institutional challenges that are the results of the decentralization; a Crypto based system will render monetary policies much harder to implement on central banks, as a result hyperinflation may occur and unemployment would be harder to control.

5 Conclusion

This study addresses one of the most contemporary economic challenges: the emerging crisis of the US Dollars. Alarming trends that have begun to materialize across the global economy, most notably, the surpassing of U.S. Treasury bills by gold reserves for the first time in two decades. By applying a combination of GARCH modelling, Monte Carlo simulation, and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, the results confirm that the U.S. dollar remains the most stable and resilient option despite significant challenges.

Findings indicate that the cryptocurrencies cannot serve as a viable substitute for the USD, since they are more speculative commodities than a currency, characterized by extreme volatility and regulatory uncertainty, especially when exposed to shocks. Gold, while a non-liability reserve asset increasingly in demand by central banks, also faces its own limitations, especially in transactional efficiency and settlement capacity, making it impractical to be the foundation of the global system. In order to estimate a timeline for potential undesirable De-dollarization, a Monte Carlo simulation was conducted. Results showed that while debt is increasing, U.S. Debt-to-GDP is unlikely to cross the 200% threshold before the 2040s–2050s, which means that the system remains stable for now. The Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) revealed that the U.S. dollar system ranks first in stabilizing global financial conditions and in promoting a sustainable and secure international financial and payment system.

In conclusion, the study finds that the world still needs the US dollar and is unlikely to lose its dominance in the short term. Despite rising debt and increasing challenges, the dollars remain the least risky and most functional global reserve system, outperforming other alternatives like gold and crypto. As a result, instead of replacing it, the US dollars should be reinforced by modernizing financial infrastructure to sustain stability, prosperity and meet challenges. Future research should place greater emphasis on examining how innovations such as CBDCs and tokenized assets, might complement or potentially disrupt the dollar system. Moreover, forthcoming studies should elevate the importance of ESG considerations in assessing reserve assets, whether dollar-based, gold-backed, or crypto-centric, by integrating factors such as carbon footprints, resource intensity, and social inclusiveness into the evaluation of long-term financial sustainability.

6 References

6.1 Articles and Reports

Bank for International Settlements (2023, June). *BIS Annual Economic Report 2023*. <https://www.bis.org/publ/arpdf/ar2023e.htm> (Bank for International Settlements)

Bank for International Settlements (2024, June). *BIS Quarterly Review*. https://www.bis.org/publ/qtrpdf/r_qt2406.pdf (Bank for International Settlements)

Bank for International Settlements (2024, December). *BIS Quarterly Review*. https://www.bis.org/publ/qtrpdf/r_qt2412.pdf (Bank for International Settlements)

Beainy, R. H. ., & Kamel, C. A. (2023). Finance for Life Instead of Death. *Migration Letters*, 20(6), 1051–1060. <https://doi.org/10.59670/ml.v20i6.4882>

Beainy, R. H., & Kamel, J. K. (2023). The Importance of Technology, R&D and AI in the US Economy. *Migration Letters*, 20(8), 573-584.

Bordo, M. D. (1993). The Bretton Woods international monetary system: a historical overview. In *A retrospective on the Bretton Woods system: Lessons for international monetary reform* (pp. 3-108). University of Chicago Press.

Chaanine, N., Mhanna, R. Y., Verdie, J. F., & Beainy, R. (2023). Leveraging business experience and knowledge to boost entrepreneurial achievement. *International Journal of Work Innovation*, 4(2), 104-115.

Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures (CPMI) (2025, Feb 3). *Interlinking fast payment systems to enhance cross-border payments* (Brief No. 7). <https://www.bis.org/cpmi/publ/brief7.pdf> (Bank for International Settlements)

Eichengreen, B. (2011). *Exorbitant Privilege: The Rise and Fall of the Dollar and the Future of the International Monetary System*. Oxford University Press

European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA) (2024, Dec 17). *MiCA implementing materials*. <https://www.esma.europa.eu> ... (overview) and EUR-Lex summary: application dates. (ESMA)

European Central Bank (2025, June 20). *The international role of the euro 2025*. <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/ire/ecb.ire202506.en.pdf> (European Central Bank)

Federal Reserve History (2013, November 22). *Nixon Ends Convertibility of U.S. Dollars to Gold and Announces Wage/Price Controls*. <https://www.federalreservehistory.org/essays/gold-convertibility-ends>

International Monetary Fund (2023, October). *Global Financial Stability Report: Safeguarding financial stability amid high debt and rising uncertainty*. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/GFSR/Issues/2023/10/> (IMF)

International Monetary Fund (2014, July 22). *The Bretton Woods Conference, 70 Years Later*. <https://www.imf.org/en/News/Articles/2015/09/28/04/53/sp072214>

IOSCO (2023, Nov 16). *Policy recommendations for crypto and digital asset markets*. <https://www.iosco.org/library/pubdocs/pdf/IOSCOPD747.pdf> (IOSCO)

IOSCO (2023, Dec 19). *DeFi policy recommendations* (Umbrella note & final report). <https://www.iosco.org/library/pubdocs/pdf/IOSCOPD755.pdf>; <https://www.iosco.org/library/pubdocs/pdf/ioscopd754.pdf> (IOSCO)

International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO) (2023, Nov 16). *Policy recommendations for crypto and digital asset markets*. <https://www.iosco.org/library/pubdocs/pdf/IOSCOPD747.pdf> (IOSCO)

Kamel, C., Beainy, R., & Bteish, M. (2025, October 10). *In God we trust. International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(10), 412–419. <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/25oct233>

Lin, L., & Nestarcova, D. (2019). Venture capital in the rise of crypto economy: problems and prospects. *Berkeley Bus. LJ*, 16, 533.

Prasad, E. (2014). *The Dollar Trap: How the U.S. Dollar Tightened Its Grip on Global Finance*. Princeton University Press.

Subrahmanyam, S., Azoury, N., & Sarkis, N. (2024, May). AI and business planning: Revolutionizing forecasting and resource allocation. In *2024 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Applied Informatics (ACCAI)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

Richard Hanna Beainy, Fleur Clara Khalil, & Dr. Jeanne Antonios Kaspard. (2024). Europe's Response: Impact of Sanctions on Russia . *EVOLUTIONARY STUDIES IN IMAGINATIVE CULTURE*, 1168–1185. <https://doi.org/10.70082/esiculture.vi.1274>

SWIFT (2025, July/Sept). *RMB Tracker* (June/August data). https://www.swift.com/sites/default/files/files/rmb-tracker_july-2025.pdf; .../rmb-tracker_september-2025.pdf (Swift)

World Bank (2024, January). *Global Economic Prospects 2024*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/global-economic-prospects> (World Bank)

Xu, M., Chen, X., & Kou, G. (2019). A systematic review of blockchain. *Financial innovation*, 5(1), 1-14.

Zoeller, C. J., & Bandelj, N. (2019). Crisis as opportunity: Nixon's announcement to close the gold window. *Socius*, 5, 2378023119841812.

6.2 Sites

Atlantic Council (2023, December). *Dollar Dominance Monitor*. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/programs/geoeconomics-center/dollar-dominance-monitor/> (Atlantic Council)

Bank for International Settlements – Innovation Hub (2024, June 5). *Project mBridge reaches MVP* (press). <https://www.bis.org/press/p240605.htm> (Bank for International Settlements)

Bank for International Settlements (2025, June 24). *Annual economic report 2025: III. The next-generation monetary and financial system*. <https://www.bis.org/publ/arpdf/ar2025e3.htm> (Bank for International Settlements)

CME Group (2025). *Gold futures overview*. <https://www.cmegroup.com/markets/metals/precious/gold.html> (CME Group)

Financial Stability Board (FSB) (2024, Oct 22). *G20 crypto-asset policy implementation roadmap: Status report*. <https://www.fsb.org/2024/10/g20-crypto-asset-policy-implementation-roadmap-status-report/> (Financial Stability Board)

Financial Stability Board (FSB) (2023, July 17). *High-level recommendations for global stablecoin arrangements*. <https://www.fsb.org/2023/07/high-level-recommendations-for-the-regulation-supervision-and-oversight-of-global-stablecoin-arrangements-final-report/> (Financial Stability Board)

ICE Benchmark Administration (n.d.). *LBMA Gold and Silver Price*. <https://www.ice.com/iba/lbma-gold-silver-price> (Ice)

International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2025, Apr 2). *COFER: Global FX reserves decreased in 2024Q4*. <https://data.imf.org> ... (news item). (IMF Data)

London Bullion Market Association (2025, January 29). *LBMA launches Gold Bar Integrity (GBI) Database*. <https://www.lbma.org.uk/articles/lbma-launches-gold-bar-integrity-gbi-database> (LBMA)

London Bullion Market Association (2025). *Clearing data*. <https://www.lbma.org.uk/prices-and-data/clearing-data> (LBMA)

London Bullion Market Association (2022–2025). *Russian Good Delivery bars information & updates*. <https://www.lbma.org.uk/good-delivery/russian-good-delivery-bars-update> (LBMA)

Reuters (2025, January 30). *London gold market queues up to borrow central bank gold after big shipments to US, sources say*. <https://www.reuters.com/world/uk/london-gold-market-queues-up-borrow-central-bank-gold-after-big-shipments-us-2025-01-29/> (Reuters)

Reuters (2025, March 7). *Outflow from London gold vaults to US slows down, says LBMA*. <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/outflow-london-gold-vaults-us-slows-down-says-lbma-2025-03-07/> (Reuters)

Reuters (2025, July 9). *Dollar cedes ground to euro in global reserves, IMF data shows*. (COFER summary). (Reuters)

Reuters (2025, September 17). *Gold prices retreat from record high ahead of Fed rate verdict*. <https://www.reuters.com/world/india/gold-prices-retreat-record-high-ahead-fed-rate-verdict-2025-09-17/> (Reuters)

Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) (2024, Jan 10). *Statement on the approval of spot Bitcoin ETPs*. <https://www.sec.gov/newsroom/speeches-statements/gensler-statement-spot-bitcoin-011023> (SEC)

Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) (2025, Sept 17). *Approval of generic listing standards for certain commodity-based ETPs (incl. crypto)*. (Commissioner Statements & orders). (SEC)

U.K. Government (2025, July 22). *Russia sanctions: Guidance* (Reg. 46Z11—prohibition on Russian gold imports). <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/russia-sanctions-guidance/russia-sanctions-guidance> (GOV.UK)

World Gold Council (2025, January 23). *Gold as a strategic asset: 2025 edition*. <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/research/relevance-of-gold-as-a-strategic-asset> (World Gold Council)

World Gold Council (2025, February 5). *Gold demand trends 2024: Full year*. <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/research/gold-demand-trends> (World Gold Council)

World Gold Council (2025, June 17). *Central bank gold reserves survey 2025*. <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/research/central-bank-gold-reserves-survey-2025> (World Gold Council)

World Gold Council (2025, July 31). *Gold demand trends Q2 2025*. <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/research/gold-demand-trends/gold-demand-trends-q2-2025> (World Gold Council)

World Gold Council (n.d.). *Gold and climate change research* (sector footprint \approx 0.4% of global emissions). <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/esg/gold-and-climate-change-research> (World Gold Council)

6.3 Abbreviations

AER	Annual Economic Report (of the Bank for International Settlements)
AML	Anti-Money Laundering
API	Application Programming Interface
BIS	Bank for International Settlements
BRICS	Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa
BTC	Bitcoin (asset)
CBDC	Central Bank Digital Currency
CFT	Countering the Financing of Terrorism
CIPS	Cross-Border Interbank Payment System (China)
COMEX	Commodity Exchange (part of CME Group)
COFER	Currency Composition of Official Foreign Exchange Reserves (IMF)
CPMI	Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures (at the BIS)
DeFi	Decentralized Finance
ECB	European Central Bank
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
ESMA	European Securities and Markets Authority
ETF	Exchange-Traded Fund
ETP	Exchange-Traded Product
EU	European Union
ETH	Ether (the native asset of Ethereum)
Fed	U.S. Federal Reserve System
FSB	Financial Stability Board
FT	Financial Times
FX	Foreign Exchange
G7	Group of Seven (Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, UK, U.S.)
G20	Group of Twenty (major advanced & emerging economies)
GBI	Gold Bar Integrity (LBMA initiative)
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
ICE	Intercontinental Exchange
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IOSCO	International Organization of Securities Commissions
ISO 20022	International Organization for Standardization messaging standard 20022
KPI/KPIs	Key Performance Indicator(s)
KYC	Know Your Customer
LBMA	London Bullion Market Association
MiCA	Markets in Crypto-Assets Regulation (EU)
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OTC	Over-the-Counter (bilateral markets)
OZ	Ounce (in this context, troy ounce of gold)
PAXG	PAX Gold (tokenized gold product)
PRGT	Poverty Reduction and Growth Trust (IMF)
PvP	Payment-versus-Payment (settlement mechanism)
RMB	Renminbi (Chinese currency)
RST	Resilience and Sustainability Trust (IMF)
SDR	Special Drawing Rights (IMF reserve asset)
SEC	U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication
UK	United Kingdom

USD United States Dollar

WGC World Gold Council

XAUT Tether Gold (tokenized gold product)